

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Hybrid Gabor Filter-Convolutional Neural Networks Model for Facial Emotion Recognition System

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P Deepan^{1*}, R Vidya¹, M Arsha Reddy¹, N Arul¹, J Ravichandran¹, S Dhiravidaselvi²¹ Department of CSE (AI&ML), St. Peter's Engineering College, Hyderabad, 500100, Telangana, India² Department of CSE, Roever Engineering College, Perambalur, 621212, Tamil Nadu, India

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* **Corresponding author.**

deepanp87@gmail.com

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Abstract

Objectives: This research aims to develop a hybrid facial emotion recognition system using integrated machine learning feature extraction techniques with convolutional neural networks model for improving the accuracy of facial emotion recognition (FER). **Methods:** This study introduces a novel approach that integrates various machine learning feature extraction techniques (HoG, LBP, SIFT and Gabor Filters) with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The study utilized a set of 10,500 facial emotion images of the CK+48 dataset with six different facial emotion recognition. **Findings:** The result from the experiments shows that the proposed Gabor Filter-CNN approach for estimating FER had higher accuracy as compared to other CNN, HoG-CNN, LBP-CNN, and SIFT-CNN. The specific approaches is based on the Gabor Filter – CNN paired results with an accuracy rate of 99.85% outstanding other models. **Novelty:** The proposed approach would ensure the combination of the ML extraction techniques for capturing the details of the textures/features and CNNs for other deep hierarchical features and further better prediction.

Keywords: Hybrid Model; Facial expressions; Emotion recognition approach; Machine Learning; Deep Learning; Gabor filter approach; Feature extraction; Convolutional neural network

1 Introduction

Facial expressions in recent years are gaining popularity because of its use in reading the inner thoughts of the individuals through Artificial Intelligence techniques⁽¹⁾. When combined with the capabilities of machine learning, emotional recognition can play a key part in determining what a human being is thinking. It is possible to identify emotion in order to investigate either the external actions or the inside thoughts of a human. A psychologist stated that emotions often only persist for a relatively short period of time, but moods are more subdued than emotions and tend to remain for a longer period of time. According to the psychologist, there are six distinct categories of feelings, including happy, normal, sad, surprised, fearful, angry, and disgusted⁽²⁾.

The feelings are able to be communicated even when there is no requirement for vocal interaction. The Facial Action Coding System is a method for determining the emotions conveyed by a person’s face by classifying the action units that are associated with each facial component. Text-based emotion recognition involves searching the text documents for text relating to emotions that are contained within the documents; this field is referred to as natural language processing⁽³⁾. The utterances of a few words are recognized in speech-based emotion recognition, and then the emotion is categorized based on the existence of a certain sound signal. Because of the way that different facial muscles work, the human face is the best tool for quickly determining an individual’s state of mind. Because of the way that different facial muscles work, the human face is the best tool for quickly determining an individual’s state of mind. One may determine a person’s state of mind using any one of a number of techniques, one of which is based on the geometric characteristics of the face. The spots inside the face area that serve as landmarks and are associated with a certain emotion. Some of the techniques concentrate on the region or certain face patches in order to determine the emotion⁽⁴⁾.

The detection of FER can be accomplished by the utilization of a variety of machine learning techniques, such as SVM, KNN, decision trees, random forests, and other approaches. The process of mining the information contained within the spatial-temporal domain of a picture is what constitutes the art of emotion recognition. For the purpose of the feature extraction process, FER has made use of appearance-based features such as HoG, LBP, and SIFT. Deep learning techniques, as opposed to more conventional machine learning approaches, will be utilised throughout this project with the intention of accomplishing the primary objective of the study, which is to identify the feeling conveyed by the subject’s mouth area and HOG elements⁽⁵⁾. FER methods to simplify the requirement for complicated human inspection by utilising deep learning approaches to assist simplify the process. One of the many uses of FER is the monitoring of emotions in feedback-based e-learning platforms. Other applications that are related to this include music recommendation systems that are based on human emotions and mood, as well as other applications⁽⁶⁾.

1.1 Challenges in Facial Emotion Recognition:

As shown in Figure 1, the domain of modern facial emotion recognition, there are several challenges that might potentially be surmounted, including:

- **Pose Variations:** The sensitivity of facial recognition systems to pose variations is significant.
- **Occlusion:** The problem of occlusion is a significant challenge in facial recognition systems, since it involves situations where the entire face is not fully visible or accessible for input.
- **Illumination Variation:** The process of automatic face recognition might encounter significant challenges due to variations in lighting conditions, resulting in a potential hindrance to accurate identification.

Fig 1. Different Challenges pose variation, illumination variation and shadow

In recent years, the widespread utilisation of facial emotion recognition in real-time systems has been increasingly prevalent across several domains such as machine vision, behaviour analysis, and video games. This surge in adoption may be attributed

to the advancements in information technology throughout the new age, which have facilitated the creation of highly accurate recognition algorithms. Consequently, the comprehension of human emotional expression by an HMI (Human Machine Interface) system is seen to be facile⁽⁷⁾. The advent of computer vision, artificial intelligence, pattern recognition, and image processing technologies has effectively addressed the limitations associated with conventional approaches. The utilisation of deep neural networks⁽⁸⁾ offers several advantages. Firstly, it can bypass the learning of the image features, thus reducing the need to identify them all manually. Furthermore, deep neural networks allow training the network datasets with finer details of face characteristics apart from the illumination and rotation changes. In their study, Gulati et al.,⁽⁹⁾ demonstrate that the learning characteristics of a convolutional neural network (CNN) utilised for training in face emotion identification exhibit a higher degree of consistency with the face features identified by psychologist Saravanan⁽¹⁰⁾ in the context of general facial expression. Hence, the domain of face emotion identification has emerged as a distinct area of study, yielding remarkable advancements in the realm of facial emotion analysis⁽¹¹⁾.

1.2. Limitation of the Existing Techniques:

The limitations of static images are starting to show; hence researchers are interested in examining the spatiotemporal motion features of changing emotions in video sequences. Some examples of this type of data are 3D video, stationary data taken from various angles, and non-stationary facial behavior.

1.3. Objective of this Research:

- The objective of this study is to examine and explore the machine learning feature extraction techniques employed in convolutional neural networks with the aim of enhancing the accuracy of face emotion recognition systems.
- We offer a hybrid strategy model that combines machine learning and deep learning to show how effective it is to integrate a CNN model with a Gabor filter.

2 Methodology

In this section, we have proposed the GF-CNN model by integrating the machine learning feature selection algorithm with a convolutional neural network deep learning model. The GF-CNN model consists of following two stages:

- **Machine Learning Techniques**
 1. Feature Extraction Techniques (Gabor Filter, HoG, LBP and SIFT)
- **Deep Learning CNN Model**
 1. Feature Extraction Layer
 2. Pooling Layer
 3. Flatten
 4. Fully Connected Layer
 5. Final Prediction

2.1. Feature Extraction Techniques

Features extraction methods are very crucial in the field of machine learning and computer vision as they bound the raw data into an easily manageable format by the algorithms. Four widely used techniques for feature extraction include SIFT, HoG, LBP, and Gabor. SIFT is used in recognizing objects, stitching of images, and reconstruction of three-dimensional objects and is a method which is employed in the detection and description of local features in images. It is time consuming in its mathematical calculations and has patents which restrict its use.

Edge information is formed by Feature templates and HoG is a feature descriptor that carries out object detection, especially the human body detection and works well for well-objected edges. LBP is a basic and effective texture operator which is applied to texture classification and face recognition, but it cannot handle the noise effectively and it's not good in dealing with the big difference of scale. Gabor filters work in spatial as well as the frequency domain but due to the convolution operation they are computationally expensive and the parameter selection is not easy.

Fig 2. The architecture of hybrid GF-CNN Model for FER

Fig 3. Input image and corresponding Gabor Filter extraction techniques

2.2. Convolutional Neural Network

The remarkable resemblance between deep learning algorithms and human brains has made them very popular in computer vision. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are utilized by the system for recognizing images. The three levels of a standard CNN model are shown in Figure 3. These layers consist of an input layer, many hidden layers, and an output layer. To construct the model, these three types of layers are used.

- Extracting the features (Convolutional layer)
- Dimensionality reduction (Pooling layer)
- converting 2D data into 1D (Flatten layer)
- Fully connected layer
- Final Prediction results

Convolutional, non-linear, pooling, and fully linked layers are some of the types of layers that are utilized during the processing of an image with several layers. The three dimensions that are used to characterize a layer are its height, breadth, and depth respective dimensions. The convolution layer is the name given to the initial layer of a CNN; it is the first layer. Whenever the filter is moved over the image, the original pixel values of the input image are multiplied by the values of the filter. Following that, these values are combined into a single value by joining them together. At the moment when the filter was being utilized, the spatial position of the filter is represented by a single number. This is done throughout the entirety of the image that is being submitted. The activation map for the image is highlighted by the first input layer, which is responsible for producing the activation map. This map highlights crucial sections of the image.

The second convolution layer also utilizes the activation map as an output. The input layers of the image each specify a set of coordinates that correspond to specific regions of the original image where specific features, such as curves and boundaries, may be observed. When a first convolution layer is iterated through a second convolution layer, high-level features such as

squares, hands, and feet are generated. The output of the activation map becomes increasingly intricate as the number of convolution layers it undergoes increases. As a result, the filters were able to emphasize the subtle differences in the image, such as specific colors and text. In order to maintain training time control, the pooling layer minimizes the number of parameters that must be managed. Furthermore, it ensures that the image’s essential information is preserved while simultaneously reducing its dimensionality.

2.3. Dataset Collection

In order to test the model, researchers used the CK+48 benchmark dataset. There are a total of 7 classes with a total of 10,500 facial emotion images, with 1500 images in each class. Each image has a 48 x 48 pixel resolution and uses the grey color system⁽¹²⁾. The different facial emotions categories are anger, contempt, disgust, fear, happiness, sadness and surprise. Figure 4 displays a few example images used for facial emotion recognition from the CK+48 dataset. As shown in Table 1, a training set, validation set and a testing set have been created from the dataset. The suggested hybrid GF-CNN model is trained using 70% of the dataset, while the remaining 20% is used for validation and 10% is used for testing purposes.

Fig 4. Sample Facial Emotion Expression

Table 1. Dataset split ratio

S. No.	Emotion Class	Training	Validation	Testing
1.	Anger	1050	300	150
2.	Contempt	1050	300	150
3.	Disgust	1050	300	150
4.	Fear	1050	300	150
5.	Happy	1050	300	150
6.	Sadness	1050	300	150
7.	Surprise	1050	300	150

2.4. Evaluation Metrics

We have evaluated the model with different evaluation metrics to evaluate the overall performance of the model.

- **Precision:** Precision metric is concerned with the truthfulness of the positive outcomes and a high precision means a low level of false positives.

$$P_c = t_c/n_c \quad (1)$$

where, t_c is a total number of properly classified samples in class c and n_c is a total number of samples in the class c .

- **Recall:** It measures the local optimality where all positive examples are identified. High recall ensures that the false negatives are eliminated.

$$R_c = t_c/k_c \quad (2)$$

where, t_c is a total number of properly classified samples in class c and k_c is number of samples classified as relevant to class c .

- **F1-Score:** The measures combine high precision with high recall rate which is more suitable when working with highly skewed data.

$$F_1 = (2 * (P_c * R_c)) / (P_c + R_c) \quad (3)$$

- **Accuracy:** The metric measures the correct average of the model and it is effective especially when the dataset is balanced.

$$Accuracy = \frac{t}{n} \quad (4)$$

where t is a number of properly classified samples and n is a total number of samples in a dataset.

3 Results and Discussion

The purpose of this part is to conduct an analysis of the performance and efficacy of facial emotion recognition using the hybrid GF-CNN model under the same conditions and parameters as before. In the beginning, we showed the benchmark CK+48 datasets for facial emotion recognition. After that, we analyzed the performance of all hybrid machine learning with deep learning CNN models (Traditional CNN, SIFT-CNN, LBP-CNN, HoG-CNN, and GF-CNN), and finally, we gave the experimental results for proposed models. The GF-CNN model that was proposed was constructed using the Python and Anaconda integrated development environment (IDE) tools.

3.1. Result Analysis of Hybrid with DL CN Models

In this part, we have examined the effectiveness of various integrated hybrid ML-CNN models, including traditional CNN, HoG-CNN, SIFT-CNN, LBP-CNN and Gabor Filter-CNN models. We have utilized dropout and Adam optimizers in order to circumvent the issue of over fitting concepts. Even though the traditional CNN model achieved the 91.29% performance of accuracy. So in order to increase the performance accuracy we have integrated the deep learning CNN model with machine learning techniques. There are four machine learning feature extraction techniques like HoG, SIFT, LBP and Gabor Filters are used. The integrated LBP-CNN model achieved an accuracy rate of 93.49%, which is a little bit higher than traditional CNN model. The remaining two integrated hybrid CNN models (HoG-CNN and SIFT-CNN) achieved equals to 96% of accuracy. Finally, the last integrated GF-CNN model achieved the highest accuracy rate of 99.85%.

The Figures 5, 6 and 7 shows performance accuracy and loss of all the integrated ML-CNN models. As shown in Figure 8, when compared to traditional CNN and all other integrated CNN models the GF-CNN achieved the accuracy rate 99.85% with epochs of 30.

For the human activity recognition of CK+48 human action images, we have developed hybrid Gabor-Filter with CNN model. From the experimental results, we observed that the hybrid model outperforms than other models. Also, the proposed result of hybrid model is compared with results obtained by other approaches available in literature and reported in Table 2.

Fig 5. Accuracy and Loss graphfor Traditional CNN and LBP-CNN models

Fig 6. Accuracy and Loss graph for HoG-CNN and SIFT-CNN models

Fig 7. Accuracy and Loss graph for GF-CNN model

Table 2. Performance Comparison of the Proposed Model with Literature

S. No.	Author	Model	Acc. in (%)
1.	Kumar R.S et al., (2022)	1D CNN Model	95.43
	Ambika et al., (2023)	Optimal CNN Model	95.29
3.	Ninad Mehendale (2020)	CNN Model	96
4.	Proposed Model (2024)	Gabor + CNN Model	99.43

Fig 8. Performance Analysis of Proposed Model with other detection model

4 Conclusion

The hybrid use of Gabor Filters and CNNs proved to be a superior strategy for face emotion recognition, efficiently resolving the obstacles presented by aesthetic variances in images. This hybrid strategy not only improves model accuracy, but it also shows promise for increasing human-computer interaction and contributing to mental health studies. With the proposed hybrid model (Gabor + CNN), which gives the highest accuracy as 99.43% of accuracy. The experimental results of hybrid model performance superior when compared to the other model such as CNN, HoG-CNN, LBP-CNN, and SIFT-CNN. Future research might investigate the use of this hybrid model in real-world applications and improve the integration of feature extraction approaches with sophisticated deep learning architectures.

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